
SMART BANKING SERVICES RESISTANCE FACTORS ACROSS OCCUPATION IN RAJASTHAN

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ABSTRACT

In the progressing time of internet banking, the market for these services was expected to grow at a fast pace. The service providers are keen on delivering their services through mobile platforms. Despite the infrastructure appropriation of the same, the acceptance did not grow at the same level. Though most of the literatures have followed the adoption approach, there are few reasoning out the barriers behind such resistance. This paper aims to find the effect of occupation on such resistance, in the Rajasthan. The innovation resistance model by Ram and Sheth has been adopted for the study to locate the barriers of smart banking services.

Key words: Innovation Resistance, Smart Banking Services, Occupation, Barriers

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1. INTRODUCTION

The value addition of smart banking services is beyond comparison to traditional banking services. The offerings of smart banking services have the edge of ubiquity, convenience, and cost efficiency for the consumers (Lin,2011). Even the governmental efforts towards its adoption are being made since 2016 through the demonetization and the zero-balance account opening scheme “Pradhan Mantri Jan-Dhan Yojana” since 2014. Due to resistance barriers the adoption has not been up to the mark. Previous studies have shown that resistance behavior is different than being the opposite of adoption behavior (Claudy et al.,2015 and Kleijnen et al.,2009).

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The innovation resistance model has been used in various studies of resistance towards the green products (Claudy M,2011), cars (Bessenbach N. and Sebastian Wallrapp S.,2013),organic food (Kushwah S., Dhir A., Sagar M,2019), etc., and also for finding the e-banking resistance factors in Finland(Mani Z, Chouk I., 2018),Malaysia(Teo A. et al,2013) and Korea(Bae,2018).Thus, the innovation Resistance Model of Ram and Sheth,1989 is appropriate for the study to identify the resistance barriers existing in the smart banking adoption being affected by the occupation of the respondents. The model has two types of barriers:

Functional Barriers: Existing due to the Usage barrier, Risk barrier, and Value barrier.

Psychological Barriers: Existing due to the Tradition barrier and Image barrier.

These can be further explained as:

2.1. Usage Barrier

It arises due to the inconsistency of the innovative service with the existing usage habits and practices. The variables constituting the usage barrier are:

- Easy to use
- Convenient to use
- Faster to use
- Progressive usage
- Need of usage

2.2. Risk Barrier

It rises as a concern due to the uncertainty in the usage and adoption of smart banking services. The variables comprising the risk barrier are as under:

- Screen size
- Connection error
- Wrong information
- Information theft
- Stability

2.3. Value Barrier

It arises because of the price to value derived comparison of the updated services. The variables constituting the value barrier are as under:

- Economical
- Advantageous
- Better control
- Time and space challenges
- Internet usage cost
- Smart device cost

2.4. Tradition Barrier

It arises when the innovation is inconsistent with the existing social norms of the customers. The variables comprising the tradition barrier are as under:

- Reliability
- Mandatory
- Customer Service

- Bank Visit

2.5. Image Barrier

These arises due to the stereotypes in the consumer's perception of smart banking services. The variables constructing the image barrier are as under:

- Phishing accidents fear
- Technology impression
- Good impression

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT AND OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The barriers existing amongst the individuals might vary according to their occupation since the needs and requirements for the occupation might affect the barriers of the consumer's usage of smart banking services. Thus, the objective of study is to determine the effect of occupation on the various resistance factors in adoption of Smart Banking Services.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The data collection has been done using the survey method in the state of Rajasthan. The questionnaires were distributed amongst the population of north, east, west, south, and central districts of Rajasthan. The SmartBanking Service Non-users were identified as the population for the study, based on stratified random sampling. The responses of 368 Non-users of SmartBanking Service were collected. The questionnaires consists of questions on all the variables under study i.e. Usage Barrier-5 constructs, Risk Barrier-5 constructs, Value Barrier-6constructs, Tradition barrier-4 constructs, Image barrier-3 constructs along with the demographic profile of the users.

5. HYPOTHESIS FORMULATION

1.H0: The usage barrier does not vary across the occupation.

H1: The usage barrier varies across the various occupations.

2.H0: The risk barrier does not vary across the occupation.

H1: The risk barrier does vary across the occupation.

3.H0: The value barrier varies across the occupation.

H1: The value barrier varies across different occupations.

4.H0: The traditional barrier does not vary across the occupation.

H1: The traditional barrier does vary across the occupation.

5.H0: The image barrier does not differ with the occupation.

H1: The image barrier differs across the occupation.

6. ANALYSIS

Demographic Profile of Respondents

According to Table 1, the respondents belonging to the agriculture customer groups are 22, while those who are students are 103. The business pursuing respondents is 87, while the homemaker customer groups are 36. The customer group working under employment is 57, whereas those working as professionals are 63.

Table 1 Occupation * Smart Banking Service Cross Tabulation

Occupation	Smart Banking Service Non-users
Agriculture	22
Student	103
Business	87
Homemaker	36
Employees	57
Professionals	63
Total	368

6.1. Reliability

Table 2 Reliability Analysis

Constructs	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
Usage Barrier	0.767531	5
Value Barrier	0.897628	6
Risk Barrier	0.747539	5
Tradition Barrier	0.867247	4
Image Barrier	0.773496	3

The Cronbach's alpha has been taken up to analyze the internal consistency (reliability) of the constructs. The Cronbach's alpha for the usage barrier is (0.767), for the value barrier it is (0.897), the risk barrier has (0.747), the tradition barrier has (0.867), whereas the image barrier has (0.773). According to Hair et al., (2010) the variables are considered reliable if the Cronbach's alpha exceeds 0.7.

6.2. Testing the Hypothesis-Analysis of Variance

The One-Way ANOVA has been selected to compare the means for the various barriers and to determine whether there is a significant relationship between the barriers and the occupation.

Table 3 ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Usage Barrier	Between Groups	10.931	5	2.186	1.832	.106
	Within Groups	432.032	363	1.193		
	Total	442.963	368			
Risk Barrier	Between Groups	8.913	5	1.783	2.646	.023
	Within Groups	243.866	363	.674		
	Total	252.779	368			
Value Barrier	Between Groups	7.147	5	1.429	2.693	.021
	Within Groups	192.171	363	.531		
	Total	199.318	368			
Tradition Barrier	Between Groups	15.039	5	3.008	3.812	.002
	Within Groups	285.651	363	.789		
	Total	300.690	368			
Image Barrier	Between Groups	7.592	5	1.518	4.916	.000
	Within Groups	111.804	363	.309		
	Total	119.396	368			

According to Table 3, the ANOVA analysis shows the significance at the four barriers, i.e, the Risk Barrier(.023),the Value Barrier(.021),the Tradition Barrier(.002),the Image Barrier(.000);wherein the P values are <.05.While the usage barrier does not have any significant influence on the occupation. Thus, to further determine the difference amongst the occupation based on the barriers, the post hoc test (Tukey HSD) has been conducted as follows:

Table 3.1 Multiple Comparisons						
Dependent Variable: Risk Barrier(Tukey HSD)						
(I) Occupation	(J) Occupation	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Agriculture	Student	.012	.193	1.000	-.54	.56
	Business	-.168	.196	.956	-.73	.39
	Homemaker	.319	.222	.706	-.32	.96
	Employees	.222	.206	.889	-.37	.81
	Professionals	-.047	.203	1.000	-.63	.54
Student	Agriculture	-.012	.193	1.000	-.56	.54
	Business	-.180	.120	.661	-.52	.16
	Homemaker	.306	.159	.387	-.15	.76
	Employees	.210	.135	.631	-.18	.60
	Professionals	-.059	.131	.998	-.44	.32
Business	Agriculture	.168	.196	.956	-.39	.73
	Student	.180	.120	.661	-.16	.52
	Homemaker	.486*	.163	.035	.02	.95
	Employees	.390	.140	.061	-.01	.79
	Professionals	.121	.136	.949	-.27	.51
Homemaker	Agriculture	-.319	.222	.706	-.96	.32
	Student	-.306	.159	.387	-.76	.15
	Business	-.486*	.163	.035	-.95	-.02
	Employees	-.096	.175	.994	-.60	.40
	Professionals	-.366	.171	.272	-.86	.13
Employees	Agriculture	-.222	.206	.889	-.81	.37
	Student	-.210	.135	.631	-.60	.18
	Business	-.390	.140	.061	-.79	.01
	Homemaker	.096	.175	.994	-.40	.60
	Professionals	-.270	.150	.469	-.70	.16
Professionals	Agriculture	.047	.203	1.000	-.54	.63
	Student	.059	.131	.998	-.32	.44
	Business	-.121	.136	.949	-.51	.27
	Homemaker	.366	.171	.272	-.13	.86
	Employees	.270	.150	.469	-.16	.70

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Thus, according to table 3.1, it is analyzed that there is a significant difference amongst the homemakers and business customer groups (.035). Thus, the homemakers and the business customer groups have a significant difference under the risk barrier.

Table 3.2 Multiple Comparisons
Dependent Variable: Value Barrier(Tukey HSD)

(I) Occupation	(J) Occupation	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Agriculture	Student	.308	.171	.467	-.18	.80
	Business	.070	.174	.999	-.43	.57
	Homemaker	.265	.197	.761	-.30	.83
	Employees	.257	.183	.723	-.27	.78
	Professionals	-.047	.180	1.000	-.56	.47
Student	Agriculture	-.308	.171	.467	-.80	.18
	Business	-.238	.106	.222	-.54	.07
	Homemaker	-.043	.141	1.000	-.45	.36
	Employees	-.051	.120	.998	-.40	.29
	Professionals	-.355*	.117	.030	-.69	-.02
Business	Agriculture	-.070	.174	.999	-.57	.43
	Student	.238	.106	.222	-.07	.54
	Homemaker	.194	.144	.759	-.22	.61
	Employees	.187	.124	.662	-.17	.54
	Professionals	-.117	.121	.926	-.46	.23
Homemaker	Agriculture	-.265	.197	.761	-.83	.30
	Student	.043	.141	1.000	-.36	.45
	Business	-.194	.144	.759	-.61	.22
	Employees	-.008	.155	1.000	-.45	.44
	Professionals	-.312	.152	.318	-.75	.12
Employees	Agriculture	-.257	.183	.723	-.78	.27
	Student	.051	.120	.998	-.29	.40
	Business	-.187	.124	.662	-.54	.17
	Homemaker	.008	.155	1.000	-.44	.45
	Professionals	-.304	.133	.204	-.69	.08
Professionals	Agriculture	.047	.180	1.000	-.47	.56
	Student	.355*	.117	.030	.02	.69
	Business	.117	.121	.926	-.23	.46
	Homemaker	.312	.152	.318	-.12	.75
	Employees	.304	.133	.204	-.08	.69

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

As per Table 3.2, there is a significant difference amongst the professionals and students (.030). Thus, the effect of the value barrier is significantly different amongst the professionals and the students.

Table 3.3 Multiple Comparisons
Dependent Variable: Tradition Barrier(Tukey HSD)

(I) Occupation	(J) Occupation	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Agriculture	Student	.333	.209	.602	-.27	.93
	Business	.445	.212	.291	-.16	1.05
	Homemaker	.436	.240	.458	-.25	1.12
	Employees	.827*	.223	.003	.19	1.47
	Professionals	.302	.220	.742	-.33	.93
Student	Agriculture	-.333	.209	.602	-.93	.27
	Business	.112	.129	.955	-.26	.48
	Homemaker	.103	.172	.991	-.39	.60

	Employees	.494*	.147	.011	.07	.91
	Professionals	-.030	.142	1.000	-.44	.38
Business	Agriculture	-.445	.212	.291	-1.05	.16
	Student	-.112	.129	.955	-.48	.26
	Homemaker	-.008	.176	1.000	-.51	.50
	Employees	.382	.151	.119	-.05	.82
	Professionals	-.142	.147	.928	-.56	.28
Homemaker	Agriculture	-.436	.240	.458	-1.12	.25
	Student	-.103	.172	.991	-.60	.39
	Business	.008	.176	1.000	-.50	.51
	Employees	.391	.189	.308	-.15	.93
	Professionals	-.134	.186	.979	-.67	.40
Employees	Agriculture	-.827*	.223	.003	-1.47	-.19
	Student	-.494*	.147	.011	-.91	-.07
	Business	-.382	.151	.119	-.82	.05
	Homemaker	-.391	.189	.308	-.93	.15
	Professionals	-.525*	.162	.017	-.99	-.06
Professionals	Agriculture	-.302	.220	.742	-.93	.33
	Student	.030	.142	1.000	-.38	.44
	Business	.142	.147	.928	-.28	.56
	Homemaker	.134	.186	.979	-.40	.67
	Employees	.525*	.162	.017	.06	.99

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

According to Table 3.3, there is a significant difference amongst the employees and agriculture customer groups (.003) along with the employees and the students (.011) and the employees and professional customer groups (.017). Thus, the students, agriculture, and professional's customer groups have a significant difference from the employees under the traditional barrier.

(I) Occupation	(J) Occupation	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Agriculture	Student	-.029	.131	1.000	-.40	.34
	Business	-.260	.133	.367	-.64	.12
	Homemaker	-.249	.150	.561	-.68	.18
	Employees	-.157	.139	.872	-.56	.24
	Professionals	-.426*	.138	.025	-.82	-.03
Student	Agriculture	.029	.131	1.000	-.34	.40
	Business	-.231	.081	.052	-.46	.00
	Homemaker	-.220	.108	.320	-.53	.09
	Employees	-.127	.092	.735	-.39	.14
	Professionals	-.397*	.089	.000	-.65	-.14
Business	Agriculture	.260	.133	.367	-.12	.64
	Student	.231	.081	.052	.00	.46
	Homemaker	.011	.110	1.000	-.30	.33
	Employees	.103	.095	.884	-.17	.37
	Professionals	-.166	.092	.461	-.43	.10
Homemaker	Agriculture	.249	.150	.561	-.18	.68
	Student	.220	.108	.320	-.09	.53
	Business	-.011	.110	1.000	-.33	.30

Employees	Employees	.093	.118	.970	-.25	.43
	Professionals	-.177	.116	.647	-.51	.16
	Agriculture	.157	.139	.872	-.24	.56
	Student	.127	.092	.735	-.14	.39
	Business	-.103	.095	.884	-.37	.17
	Homemaker	-.093	.118	.970	-.43	.25
	Professionals	-.270	.102	.087	-.56	.02
Professionals	Agriculture	.426*	.138	.025	.03	.82
	Student	.397*	.089	.000	.14	.65
	Business	.166	.092	.461	-.10	.43
	Homemaker	.177	.116	.647	-.16	.51
	Employees	.270	.102	.087	-.02	.56

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

According to Table 3.4, there is a significant difference amongst the professionals and agriculture customer groups (.025) along with the professionals and the students (.000). Thus, the students, agriculture, and professional's customer groups have a significant difference under the image barrier.

Hypothesis Analysis

7. RESULTS

- The occupation does not have any effect on the usage barrier.
- The occupation affects the risk barrier across the business and homemaker customer groups.
- The occupation type affects the value barrier as the student and professionals differ across the barrier.
- The type of occupation affects the traditional barrier as the students, agriculture, professionals, and employee's customer groups vary across the barrier.
- The occupation influences the image barrier, as the students, agriculture, and professional's customer groups are different under the said barrier.

Variable	Hypothesis Supported
Usage Barrier	The usage barrier is not affected by the occupation.
Risk Barrier	The risk barrier is affected and varies across the different occupations.
Value Barrier	The value barrier is influenced by the occupation.
Tradition Barrier	The tradition barrier is affected and varies across the different occupations
Image Barrier	The image barrier is affected by the occupation.

8. IMPLICATIONS

The study has stated the different occupations impact the various barriers, and thus the said barriers can be minimized by focusing on the barriers. The study could be used to support the critical groups amongst the various barriers by addressing the specific barriers across the different occupations. The information and results of the study clearly state the groups that are to be addressed to remove the said barriers. The study would act as a guideline for the future researchers in the said field, as it pinpoints the groups to be undertaken for the specific barrier removal. The study would ensure to give guidance to the policymakers to target the select groups for the resistance reduction. The various institutional efforts can be better utilized with the guidance of the study.

9. LIMITATIONS

- The study has been directed towards the occupation only, thus further factors could be undertaken in the future.
- The study has included the respondents of the Rajasthan, thus might not be generalized for the other areas.
- Pertaining to the time and cost constraints, the sample size is 368 which could have been more.

10. CONCLUSION

The study has addressed all the said objectives it was meant to analyze. The findings in the study have revealed to be significant for four out of the five barriers. The usage barrier did not influence the occupation while the risk barrier, value barrier, tradition barrier, and image barrier had been influenced by the occupation type of the customer groups.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bae J.K. (2018). A Study on the Determinant Factors of Innovation Resistance and Innovation Acceptance on Internet Primary Banks. *Proceedings of the 20th Asia-Pacific Conference on Global Business, Economics, Finance & Social Sciences (API8Hong Kong Aug Conference)*, (pp. 1-7). Hong Kong.
- [2] Bessenbach N., W. S. (2013). *Why do Consumers resist buying Electric Vehicles?* Copenhagen: Copenhagen Business School.
- [3] Claudy M.C.C. (2011). *An Empirical Investigation of Consumer Resistance to Green Product Innovation*. Dublin: School of Marketing, University of Dublin.
- [4] Claudy, M. (2015). Consumer resistance to innovation-a behavioral reasoning perspective. *Journal of Academic Marketing Science* 43(4), 528-544.
- [5] Inès Chouk, Z. M. (2019). Factors for and against resistance to smart services: the role of consumer lifestyle and ecosystem related variables. *Journal of Services Marketing*, 1-16.
- [6] Kleijnen, M. (2009). An exploration of consumer resistance to innovation and its antecedents. *Journal of Economic Psychology* 30, 344-357.
- [7] Kushwah, S. D. (2019). Understanding Consumer Resistance to Consumption of Organic Food. A Study of Ethical Consumption, Purchasing, and Choice Behaviour, Food Quality, and Preference. *Food Quality and Preference*, 1-14.
- [8] Lin, H. (2011). An empirical investigation of mobile banking adoption: The effect of innovation attributes and knowledge-based trust. *International Journal of Information Management* .31(3), 252-260.
- [9] Ram, S. a. (1989). "Consumer resistance to innovations: the marketing problem and its solutions. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, Vol. 6 No. 2, 5-14.
- [10] Teo C.A., C. C. (2013). Why consumers resist mobile banking? A conceptual model. *International Conference on Technology Innovation and Industrial Management*, (pp. 1-5). Phuket, Thailand.